

THE ROLE OF FRANCE IN INTERNATIONAL RELATIONS DURING THE GREAT FRENCH REVOLUTION.

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Abstract: This article examines international relations during the revolutionary processes in France between 1789 and 1799, including the coalitions formed by the leading Western European powers against France, the isolation of France, and Europe in the last decade of the 18th century. The political processes that took place in the diplomacy have been revealed.

Key words: the struggle for the Spanish throne, the Seven Years' War, the first coalition, natural borders, blue water strategy, the battle near the Ehrams, diplomacy.

Today, a tense geopolitical situation prevails in the world, which we can see in the example of the Russian-Ukrainian war currently taking place in the world. Right now, against the backdrop of the Russia-Ukraine war, the world's leading countries are fighting for hegemony, and this struggle certainly has negative effects on many countries of the world. If we look at history under the influence of this struggle, we will see that there have been many such struggles in history. In particular, if we pay attention to the European countries in terms of hegemony, we can see that mainly two countries fought for hegemony in these regions, and we can understand that the fate of many countries involuntarily depends on these two countries. The two most powerful countries of Europe are France and Great Britain, and we can see in many historical data that the whole century passed under the struggle of these two countries. It was these two countries that formed the European power system, and we can witness that the competition between these two countries intensified in the 18th century and reached a new level

with the beginning of the French Revolution, which took an important place in the history of the world by the end of the century.

In particular, France fought many foreign wars in the international arena in the 17th and 18th centuries. By this time, France had lost a number of wars, for example, in the war for the Spanish throne in 1701-1714 and in the "Seven Years' War" in 1756-1763. After the defeat in these wars, the hegemony passed to Great Britain. Because Great Britain was considered to have great superiority at sea, and for this reason France maintained a large army on land as the main competitor of Great Britain. On the eve of the French revolution, a balance of power was formed in Europe, and they were Great Britain, France, Austria, Prussia and Russia, and these countries occupied a leading position in international relations.

At the end of the 18th century, in addition to the above factors, changes in international relations occurred due to the beginning of the French Revolution. In 1789, the absolute monarchy of King Louis XVI in France fell due to a revolution in the country. This event led European countries to take action against the French Revolution. Because of this, they were afraid that the revolution that started in France would be exported to them, and immediately on August 27, 1791, a declaration was signed between Austria and Prussia in Pilnitz Castle. On February 7, 1792, a military alliance was formed against France, and thus, the first coalition of European countries against France was founded.

The formation of such an attitude against the French Revolution was different, and the views of research scientists were also different. In particular, the formation of these relations can be explained by the conflict of interests between major countries. In some views, despite its anti-absolutist character, the French Revolution did not provoke hostility from the European powers in the early stages of its development, but it did not deny the possibility of armed intervention in the future. A number of European countries benefited from the chaos that reigned after the revolution in France. Also, Great Britain was the first to take advantage of these revolutionary disturbances in France and tried to seize French colonial

territories. Prussia has been in conflict with the Bourbons since the time of Frederick II, and he was looking to take advantage of this situation to gain a dominant position in Western Europe. Nevertheless, the collapse of the Bourbon power in France caused serious problems for most European countries. One such country was Austria, which lost its foreign ally France and became isolated against its rivals Great Britain and Prussia. In foreign policy, Austria agreed to the alliance with Russia only because of the war with Turkey.

In fact, the revolution started in France by the end of the 18th century, and the international relations that have been going on until that time changed the system. The French Revolution also caused a conflict of interests among other great powers. In particular, such countries are Great Britain and Russia, at this time, due to the revolution, France gave up active foreign policy in 1789-1791, because at the same time there was no clear power structure in France, and the struggle for power began. This situation allowed the British Prime Minister Pitt Jr. to turn his attention to Eastern Europe to counter the further expansion of Russian influence, ignoring his arch-rival. Based on an alliance with Prussia and the Netherlands, he demanded that Russia renounce all gains made in the war with Turkey and threatened armed intervention in its Triple Alliance. Naturally, in such a situation, Russian Empress Catherine II was forced to look for an ally to withstand the pressure of Great Britain and Prussia, and started negotiations with France as an ally. However, this union disappeared due to the weakness of the Bourbon monarchy against the revolution in the country. Social changes in France between 1789 and 1791 did not play an important role in comparison to either autocratic Russia or constitutional liberal Great Britain. Because Great Britain saw the French Revolution as a continuation of the English Revolution and was ready to come to an agreement with the new French government in order to limit the success of Russia. On the other hand, against the background of increasing internal "anarchy", which weakened its arch-rival, Great Britain allowed the unhindered expansion of its colonial empire around the world. Also, for Catherine II, the

restriction of royal rights in France, the severity of the foreign political situation did not allow her to express her monarchical feelings, but forced her to seek a consensus with the new government of France. At the same time, as a result of the abandonment of France's previous positions in Eastern Europe and Turkey, it allowed Russia to increase its influence in these regions. This was the emergence of Great Britain-Russia opposition around the French Revolution.

An important event in the international relations of this period was the existence of territorial claims between France and the Holy Roman Empire. In particular, France was able to avoid territorial conflicts with the Holy Roman Empire due to the selected foreign policy tactics.

France's return to the concept of "natural borders" was connected with the Great French Revolution, which caused new conflicts with the German principalities.

This primarily affected the German principalities that were under the influence of France. Seeing that the revolutionary events in France were undermining the foundations of the feudal system, the princes began to fear their rights and privileges and asked for help from the Emperor of Austria (Holy Roman Empire). Secondly, it was a reason for Austria to interfere in the internal affairs of France, and it should be added that the wife of the French king, Marie-Antoinette, was the sister of the Austrian empress. Also, the principalities on the left bank of the Rhine sponsored emigrants from France, who created the center of the French counter-revolution in their territories, and this situation became increasingly clear that it would lead to an armed conflict between them.

In the first years of the revolutionary events, it was announced that France would adhere to the principles of equal rights of all peoples and rejection of all forms of violence, as defined in the Constitution of 1791. However, the changed internal and external political situation forced changes in international activities. On the eve of the French Revolution, the political interests of France and the German states took such a form.

Thus, the outbreak of a new war in Europe presented France with a new bourgeois character with the need to defend itself, and attack was chosen as the best defense, which required a concept with clear foundations. The leading figures of the French Revolution returned to the foreign policy of France the doctrine of the old regime - "natural limits" and made its provisions the basis of the military plan of 1792. Those who put this concept into practice were considered representatives of the formation of a new revolution. Therefore, they gave it a new dimension: the expansion of the "natural limits" was now associated with the spread of the revolution. By these "natural frontiers" the leaders of the French Revolution understood the territories that resembled their regime. In fact, the doctrine of "natural limits" put forward in 1792-1794 became a means of "exporting the revolution" and this idea dominated French foreign policy.

A coalition against France was quickly formed in Europe and they tried to forcefully interfere in France's internal affairs. And in France, this news intensified the patriotic movement, and the country's Legislature declared that "the Fatherland is in danger." As mentioned above, the French revolutionary government did not wait for the attack, but took the initiative and declared war on Austria. At first, the French army, which was not ready for war, invaded the territory of Belgium and was defeated. After some time, the threat of a real invasion of France by foreign invaders appeared, and most of the hostilities began without success for France. Also, Prussia was acting in alliance with Austria, whose army invaded French territory and occupied a number of fortresses. In such conditions, mobilization was announced in France, volunteer detachments were formed throughout the country and gathered in Paris. The population saw the monarchy as the reason for the military failure, and because of this, the discontented mood in the country that wanted to destroy the monarchy grew stronger. In particular, this protest turned into an uprising after the commander of the Prussian troops, Duke Braunschweig, threatened the inhabitants of the capital to punish those who harmed the king. As a

result of this uprising, on August 10, 1792, King Louis XVI was overthrown in France and the monarchy collapsed in the country.

After the surrender of Longwy and Verdun fortresses in September 1792, the invaders approached the capital. In the same situation, the French unexpectedly successfully repulsed the Prussian attack at the Battle of Valmy, and after this battle, the French Revolutionary Army occupied Belgium and the left bank of the Rhine, Nice and Savoy. Part of these occupied lands was annexed to France. However, the king's execution alarmed many European monarchs, and Britain and Spain later joined the coalition. And Russia provided financial support to the army of émigrés fighting the revolution outside France. With the establishment of the Jacobin dictatorship in France, the French army completely freed its territory from intervention at the beginning of 1794 and managed to transfer the war to the enemy's territory. In June 1794, the French army defeated the Austrian army in a battle near the Belgian village of Fleuris, and thus the first coalition was defeated.

The weakness and ineffectiveness of the first coalition in international relations, caused by the opposition between the Allies on the "Polish question" and the goals and means of the war with France, caused a series of defeats of the first coalition. In 1794, Prussia's withdrawal from the war with France, Austria's weakness and Russia's refusal to provide any assistance, their open aggressive policy towards Poland caused a sharp criticism of the idea of an alliance with the continental powers in Great Britain. On the one hand, this led to the strengthening of the traditional isolation of Great Britain with the "Blue Water" strategy, which involved concentrating all of its resources on maritime colonial invasions rather than on international wars, and on the other hand, Great Britain pitted European powers against France. advocated involvement in active struggle. This shows that the first coalition formed against France was not strong, and the existence of disagreements between them came to the hands of the leaders of the French Revolution.

In France itself, those who came to power after the collapse of the Jacobin dictatorship as a result of the 9 Thermidore counter-revolutionary coup d'état were collectively called Thermidores and began to rule the government.

Despite increasing internal political instability during Thermidor's rule, France's international position improved considerably. In particular, in December 1794, the 17-month attack of the French army on Holland ended successfully, and on January 19, 1795, the French entered Amsterdam. In the Netherlands, the power of the Stadthausers was overthrown, and the Republic of Batavia was established in its place.

The new French government instead advocated the preservation of the country's "natural borders" (along the Rhine, the Alps, and the Pyrenees) and then abandoned expansion. On February 9, 1795, a peace treaty was signed between France and Tuscany, and on April 5, a treaty was signed between France and Prussia. According to this treaty, France continued to occupy the left bank of the Rhine until peace was made with the German Empire.

Despite the collapse of the first coalition formed against the French, Great Britain and Austria decided to continue the struggle against the ongoing revolutionary processes in France. In particular, in 1795, an alliance was formed with Russia, and even Empress Catherine II intended to send an army under the command of Suvorov to the Rhine. However, due to the death of Catherine II and the policies of Paul I, who came to the throne, this project was not realized. During this period, significant changes took place in France itself, in particular, the power of the country now passed into the hands of the Directory, and they began to act more aggressively in the matter of foreign policy.

At first, control over diplomacy was transferred to the hands of army generals, from 1797 - S.M., who was considered a resourceful and talented diplomat of his time. Talleyrand began to lead the Ministry of Foreign Affairs. The Directory also pursued an active foreign policy, resuming traditional efforts to oust the Habsburgs from Northern Italy and strengthen French influence in the

Mediterranean and the Middle East. It should be noted here that wherever the French army went, with the help of the middle classes, peasants and artisans, it abolished many feudal systems and established the modern systems created by the revolution. As mentioned above, the wars waged by France against the European kingdoms during the Directory period have gradually turned into a war of conquest and wealth. This can be seen from the fact that in the areas where the French army entered, the main goal was to seize money, food stocks, rare paintings, figurines and works of art. These seized items were transported to Paris as war booty. These events led to the emergence of negative views of the French Revolution.

The war continued in Europe, and during the campaign of 1796, the French army set itself the task of breaking the resistance of Great Britain and Austria. Therefore, a plan was developed in this regard, according to the plan, Moreau and Jourdan's armies would deliver the main blow in the southern German territories, and the Italian front would be considered as an auxiliary front, where a small army would be gathered under the leadership of the young general Napoleon Bonaparte, and General Gosch He had to prepare for landing in Ireland.

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